

Gender-Responsive Management in Higher Education and Research

Dr. Swati Lodha¹

¹ Director, MET Institution of Management, Mumbai, India

ABSTRACT

The paper delves into the origins and characteristics of gender disparities in education and science across multiple regions, including Europe, America, Southeast Asia, the Middle East, and North Africa. The primary hypothesis posits a connection between gender imbalances in education and societal development metrics, like the Human Development Index and educational attainment. The study draws upon data spanning the years 1950 to 2021, collected from reputable sources such as the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the World Economic Forum, and the United Nations. An analysis of the Gender Equality Index from 1950 to 2000 highlights noteworthy gender gaps in select countries, notably with Eastern and Western Europe exhibiting higher levels of development compared to other areas. Furthermore, the research uncovers a substantial correlation between a nation's level of human development and the extent of gender inequality in education, indicating that increased development leads to a reduction in educational disparities between genders. Additionally, the study reveals a disparity in the publication output of men and women in scientific research, with only 22.07% of publications authored by women. This gender imbalance can be attributed to various factors, including limited opportunities for fieldwork, restricted access to training programs, time constraints impeding research endeavors, gender-based discrimination stemming from personal interests, and the burdens of family responsibilities.

Keywords: *Gender disparities, Education, Societal development, Human Development Index, Scientific research*

INTRODUCTION

Gender equality has become an imperative in today's world, extending to all spheres of life, including higher education and research. In academia, gender-responsive management is essential to ensure that women and other marginalized genders have equal opportunities and support to thrive in their academic and research careers. This article explores the significance of gender-responsive management in higher education and research, delving into the challenges and opportunities it presents. Gender inequality is a phenomenon characterised by the presence of discriminatory practises that hinder men and women from accessing and benefiting from social, economic, and political systems equally. It also involves the marginalisation of women in the process of empowering societal decision-making. The Global Gender Gap Report-2008 posited that gender inequality arises from the enduring prejudice faced by a specific demographic that has greater power in terms of race, culture, politics, and economics compared to other demographics. Gender inequality can be attributed to various factors, including disparities in educational access, differential employment opportunities, discriminatory practises in the workplace, unequal treatment under legal protection, limited bodily autonomy, inadequate healthcare facilities, lack of religious freedom, insufficient political representation, racism, and societal attitudes (Soken-Huberty, n.d.).

According to Sen's (1992) theoretical framework, gender inequality arises from disparities in the distribution of income within households, as well as variations in resource allocation and the subsequent conversion of these resources into the ability to operate effectively. It is an established reality that women residing in rural areas of Asia and North Africa experience distinct forms of gender-based treatment in comparison to men. The observed illness and death rates indicated a significant disparity in the deprivation experienced by females, particularly in terms of differential attainment inequality and shortfall inequality. Gender disparities are prevalent in Sub-Saharan Africa, mostly attributed to factors such as limited literacy and numeracy skills, underrepresentation in leadership positions, and inadequate opportunities for professional advancement. Gender inequality is a multifaceted issue that can be attributed to various factors, including but not limited to poverty, low literacy rates, high unemployment rates, entrenched societal conventions and practises, prevailing social

attitudes, and a lack of awareness regarding the rights and capabilities of women. Numerous factors contribute to the occurrence of violence against women and the perpetuation of gender-based power imbalances within society. Imbalances of varying degrees are present in all communities worldwide. According to Manjulata and Sapna (2018), it is commonly asserted that gender inequality in the education system arises as a result of sex discrimination experienced along individuals' educational trajectories across their lifetimes.

Currently, as of 2023, the global gender gap is recorded at 68.4% across 146 countries. The educational attainment rate stands at 95.2% for these countries. Among the regions, Europe has the highest gender gap at 76.3%, followed by North America at 75%, Latin America and the Caribbean at 74.3%, Eurasia and Central Asia at 69%, East Asia and the Pacific at 68.8%, Sub-Saharan Africa at 68.2%, Southern Asia at 63.4%, and the Middle East and North Africa at 62.6%. Based on their respective rankings, the four countries that occupy the top positions are Iceland, Norway, Finland, and New Zealand, with corresponding Human Development Index (HDI) values of 0.912, 0.879, 0.863, and 0.866, respectively. India is positioned at the 127th rank with an index value of 0.643, placing it below countries such as Bangladesh, Nepal, and Bhutan. The lowest places are held by Chad (146th) and Afghanistan (145th). According to the education inequality index, India occupied the 26th position, while Argentina attained the top place. In the context of regional gender disparities, Moldova has the top position in Euro Asia with an index value of 0.788. New Zealand achieved the highest ranking in the East Asia and Pacific region, attaining an index score of 0.856. According to the Global Gender Gap Index (2023) published by the World Economic Forum, Nicaragua attained the highest ranking in Latin America and the Caribbean, with an index of 0.811. In the Middle East and North Africa region, the United Arab Emirates secured the top position with an index of 0.712. Canada maintained its first rank in North America, with an index of 0.770. In South Asia, Bangladesh emerged as the leading country with a rank of one and an index of 0.722, followed by Bhutan, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Maldives, and India. Namibia achieved the highest ranking in sub-Saharan Africa, with an index of 0.802, while Chad ranked last (146th) with an index of 0.570.

Based on data provided by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), it is observed that a higher proportion of male graduates in the fields of Physics,

Mathematics, and Engineering, specifically 71%, are employed in professional occupations. In contrast, the corresponding figure for female graduates stands at 43%. Sex discrimination is prevalent in high schools and colleges, resulting in limited opportunities for women to secure high-paying positions for which they are qualified. Sex discrimination in the realm of education has been found to contribute to the development of subservient behaviour, less vocalisation, and diminished self-confidence among females. This phenomenon can be attributed to the presence of a hidden curriculum, as described by Wikipedia (n.d.). According to a news release by UNICEF (n.d.), there exists a global disparity in educational access, with a staggering 129 million females being deprived of schooling. Among this population, 32 million are enrolled in primary school, 30 million in lower-secondary school, and 67 million in upper-secondary school. The presence of gender parity in primary schools is observed in a mere 49% of nations, while lower secondary education demonstrates this phenomenon in 42% of countries, and upper secondary education lags behind with just 24% of countries achieving gender parity. However, it is worth noting that the disparities between genders tend to widen when students progress to the secondary level of education.

The analysis of the historical Gender Equality Index from 1950 to 2000 reveals notable trends among world regions in four key dimensions: health, socio-economic resources, gender disparities in households, and gender disparities in politics. Figure 1 provides a visual representation of the scores. The findings indicate that Eastern and Western Europe have experienced rapid progress compared to other regions. Nevertheless, it is evident that South and South-East Asia, the Middle East, and North Africa exhibited significant disparities and achieved the lowest scores in comparison to other regions. Latin America experienced a significant rise in levels of equality.

Furthermore, an analysis of regional gender equality and its trends between 2006 and 2023 revealed that Europe and North America have exhibited more rapid progress in achieving gender equality compared to other regions. Latin America and East Asia have also made notable advancements, albeit at a slower pace. In contrast, the Middle East, North Africa, and South Asia have experienced sluggish progress in this regard, resulting in their lower rankings (see Figure-2).

In the realm of academic research, a study conducted in the United States utilised regression analysis to examine the relationship between the percentage of female researchers and the gender inequality index. The sample size consisted of 1000 individuals. The findings revealed a positive association between these variables, with a correlation coefficient of 0.21 (Cabolis, 2018). According to a study conducted by Cislak, Formanowicz, and Saguy (2018), an analysis of peer-reviewed articles published in 2534 journals between 2008 and 2015 indicated that 31.65% of articles published prior to 2008 and 31.71% of articles published within the same period were recognised as exhibiting gender bias.

Another significant study has indicated that male researchers have a higher perception of gender equality inside their department compared to their female counterparts, with the United Kingdom exhibiting a more favourable situation in this regard. Spain had a higher degree of gender imbalance in the allocation of resources pertaining to professional development in comparison to the United Kingdom. The proportion of women occupying high positions in academia is 44% in the United Kingdom, while in Spain, it is at 41%. The

process of decision-making is also subject to the influence of substantial biases. The present investigation was conducted by García-González, Forcén, and Jimenez-Sanchez (2019), wherein they employed Principal Component Analysis in conjunction with two-way ANOVA models, which were subsequently validated using the Cronbach Alpha test and Cohen's d test. The study encompassed a sample of 1295 researchers from the United Kingdom and Spain, and data collection took place between the 5th of February 2018 and the 4th of May 2018. The primary focus of the study was to examine the perceptions of these researchers regarding gender equality.

Within the current context of gender inequality in education, the author aims to elucidate the inherent characteristics and enduring framework of gender disparities in education, particularly within the realm of higher education and research. The author also seeks to explicate the interplay between human development and gender inequality, as well as other relevant indicators, with a specific focus on a case study pertaining to the involvement of women in research publications. Furthermore, the author endeavours to identify the factors that contribute to the limitations faced by female researchers. The present study examines policy recommendations aimed at enhancing gender equality in higher education and research. In the realm of academic research, a study conducted in the United States utilised regression analysis to examine the relationship between the percentage of female researchers and the gender inequality index. The sample size consisted of 1000 individuals. The findings revealed a positive association between these variables, with a correlation coefficient of 0.21 (Cabolis, 2018). According to a study conducted by Cislak, Formanowicz, and Saguy (2018), an analysis of peer-reviewed articles published in 2534 journals between 2008 and 2015 indicated that 31.65% of articles published prior to 2008 and 31.71% of articles published within the same period were recognised as exhibiting gender bias.

Another significant study has indicated that male researchers have a higher perception of gender equality inside their department compared to their female counterparts, with the United Kingdom exhibiting a more favourable situation in this regard. Spain had a higher degree of gender imbalance in the allocation of resources pertaining to professional development in comparison to the United Kingdom. The proportion of women occupying high positions in academia is 44% in the United Kingdom, while in Spain, it is at 41%. The

process of decision-making is also subject to the influence of substantial biases. The present investigation was conducted by García-González, Forcén, and Jimenez-Sanchez (2019), wherein they employed Principal Component Analysis in conjunction with two-way ANOVA models, which were subsequently validated using the Cronbach Alpha test and Cohen's d test. The study encompassed a sample of 1295 researchers from the United Kingdom and Spain, and data collection took place between the 5th of February 2018 and the 4th of May 2018. The primary focus of the study was to examine the perceptions of these researchers regarding gender equality.

Within the current context of gender inequality in education, the author aims to elucidate the inherent characteristics and enduring framework of gender disparities in education, particularly within the realm of higher education and research. The author also seeks to explicate the interplay between human development and gender inequality, as well as other relevant indicators, with a specific focus on a case study pertaining to the involvement of women in research publications. Furthermore, the author endeavours to identify the factors that contribute to the limitations faced by female researchers. The present study examines policy recommendations aimed at enhancing gender equality in higher education and research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Author (Year)	Major Findings
Klasen and Lamanna (2008)	Gender inequality in education and employment reduces economic growth; examined from 1960-2000 worldwide.
Nmadu, Avidime, Oguntunde, Dashe, Abdulkarim, and Mandara (2010)	Gross Enrolment Ratio (GER) in Northern Nigeria showed disparities between males and females in primary school.
Reeves, Buckner, and Smith (2021)	In the USA, more girls graduated than boys in all states in 2017-18; graduation rates varied among different

	student groups.
Hao, Zhang, and Yu (2021)	Rural education in China revealed gender disparities in years of education spent, influenced by various demographic factors.
EU Commission (n.d.)	Gender inequality still exists in research despite an increase in women achieving PhDs; funds are sanctioned to address this.
Tzilivakis (2022)	The EU Commission is allocating funds for gender equality in research and innovation programs at higher education institutions.
European Institute for Gender Equality (2016)	Gender Equality Plans in research aim to create structural changes using various tools and resources.
Huang, Gates, Sinatra, and Barabási (2020)	Gender disparities exist in scientific publications, with fewer female authors and productivity gaps between genders.
Casad, Franks, Garasky, Kittleman, Roesler, Hall, and Petzel (2020)	Gender disparities in STEM fields are due to factors like stereotype representation and academic environments.
Luo, Guo, and Li (2021)	Gender equality has improved in Chinese higher education with no significant gender gaps in access to elite universities.
Liu, Holme, Chiesa, AlShebli, and Rahwan (2023)	A gender gap exists among editors of scientific journals, with a disparity in publication records between male and female editors.

SCOPE OF THE PAPER: The primary objective of this paper is to focus on the issue of gender inequality in education, with a specific emphasis on higher education and research within various global regions. The paper aims to investigate the underlying causes of persistent, long-term structural gender inequality, explore the intricate relationship between human development and gender disparities, and identify suitable policy recommendations as proposed by international organizations. Additionally, the paper includes a case study on the involvement of women in research publication and provides insights into the factors contributing to gender-based limitations.

METHODOLOGY: The author of this paper employed a comprehensive methodology that involved the use of data, trend lines, and factual information pertaining to gender inequality, particularly in the realm of higher education. The data sources utilized in this research include the OECD (2021), the World Economic Forum (2023), the World Economic Forum Global Gender Gap Index (2023), UNICEF Reports, Human Development Reports, and the Inequality-adjusted Education Index (2021). In the case study investigating gender inequality in research, the author examined 50 international journals, book collections from organizations such as the Bengal Economic Association and the Indian Economic Association, and books authored by esteemed professors from academic institutions in India and abroad. The author conducted an in-depth analysis that incorporated numerous references to delve into the causes, structural changes, and international policies related to gender inequality in higher education and research.

Causes of Gender Inequality in Education:

1. Jacobs (1996) highlighted that gender inequality in higher education often stems from disparities in social class and ethnicity.
2. Clark (1992) suggested that in developing countries, a higher influx of multinational investments is associated with reduced access to higher education for girls.
3. Salik and Zhiyong (2014) argued that gender inequality and discrimination in higher education can impede economic growth, hinder gender development, and perpetuate poverty and vulnerability in society.

4. Rosa Clavero (2022) exposed the primary reason for gender inequality in higher education and research, indicating that men hold dominant roles within academic systems, while women are often relegated to subordinate positions.
5. Silander et al. (2013) observed that gender inequality in higher education exhibits both vertical and horizontal segregation, where male and female-dominated disciplines differ, necessitating tailored solutions.
6. Karak and Sen (2017) focused on gender inequalities in various dimensions of the Indian education system, identifying gender discrimination in economic, social, cultural, and legal domains. They utilized the Women's Economic Opportunity Index to quantify these disparities.
7. World Bank (2023) highlighted the substantial gender gap in education, revealing that girls lag behind boys at all levels of education, with poverty being a significant barrier to girls' access to education.
8. British Council (2021) conducted research in Andhra Pradesh, finding disparities in female gross enrollment ratios and gender parity indices in higher education. These disparities are attributed to increased education costs, limited employment opportunities, language challenges, and a predominantly male teaching staff.
9. Slaughter (1993) argued that gender disparities in faculties are due to the dominance of men in colleges and universities, as women with PhDs are relatively scarce, affecting the representation of women in high-achieving positions.

Human Development and Inequality in Education: The Human Development Index is positively associated with the Education Index. Generally, countries with high human development levels are expected to have higher education indices, although exceptions exist. The analysis of linear trend lines for different groups of human development countries from 1990 to 2021 reveals specific country trends, such as Switzerland's consistent improvement in its HDI, while other countries, like Albania, the Philippines, India, Tanzania, and Niger, show varying rates of HDI increase over time.

Figure 3. HDI Trends

In general, there exists a positive correlation between the Human Development Index (HDI) and the Education Index, indicating that as the HDI increases, so does the education index. However, when considering the impact of gender disparity on the education index and subsequently on the human development index, it becomes evident that the situation must undergo a transformation. Switzerland holds the top position in the Human Development Index (HDI). However, after accounting for gender inequality, it is ranked third due to a 0.6 difference in the pass rate for secondary education between boys and females. However, there is a marginal difference of 0.1 seen in the case of Denmark, which holds the top position in the gender inequality index. North Macedonia is positioned at the 37th place among nations with good human development, as indicated by its gender inequality index score of 0.134. Notably, there exists a disparity of 13.2 in the secondary education pass rates between males and girls in the country. Nevertheless, Mexico is positioned at the 75th rank with a gender disparity index score of 0.309, indicating a mere 1.6 discrepancy in the secondary school completion rates between boys and females. Tajikistan is positioned at the 68th rank in terms of medium human development. It exhibits a gender inequality score of 0.370, indicating the presence of gender disparities. Furthermore, there is a 1.1% disparity in the secondary pass level between males and girls in Tajikistan. India is positioned at 122nd place on the gender inequality index, with a score of 0.490. However, there exists a 12%

disparity in the secondary pass rates between boys and females in the country. Among countries with poor levels of human development, Yemen holds the highest rank at 170. It exhibits a gender inequality score of 0.820, indicating significant disparities between males and females. Specifically, there is a notable discrepancy of 15.1% in the secondary pass rates between boys and females. Ethiopia has a favourable value of 0.520, positioning it at rank 129. Notably, a discernible gender disparity of 11% exists in the secondary pass rate within the country. Hence, it can be observed that in nations characterised by elevated levels of human development, there exists a notable reduction in gender inequality, as evidenced by the small disparity in educational attainment between males and girls. In contrast, low human development countries exhibit the opposite phenomenon. However, it is worth noting that in nations with medium levels of human development, there exist varying observations in the gender equality index as well as disparities in the education levels between males and females (refer to Table 1).

Table 1. Gender Inequality Index and Educational Level

Countries	Gender Inequality index	Rank (2021)	At least secondary level pass	
			Female (%)	Male (%)
Very high human development				
Denmark	0.03	1	95.1	95.2
Norway	0.06	2	99.1	99.3
Switzerland	0.018	3	96.9	97.5
High human development				
North Macedonia	0.134	37	61.9	75.1
Bosnia-Herzegovina	0.136	38	82.7	94.0
Albania	0.144	39	95.4	93.0
China	0.192	48	78.3	85.4
Cuba	0.303	73	89.5	91.9
Mexico	0.309	75	65.1	66.7
Medium human development				
Tajikistan	0.370	68	93.5	94.6
Bhutan	0.415	98	23.6	32.3
India	0.490	122	41.8	53.8
Bangladesh	0.530	131	50.6	58.5

It is important to acknowledge that within countries classified as having high levels of human development, Czechia exhibits the lowest level of educational disparity at 1.3%, followed by Slovakia at 1.7%, New Zealand at 1.8%, and Russia at 2.0%, among others. In contrast, the inequality-adjusted education index reveals a different ranking, with New Zealand occupying the top position with a score of 0.914. Following closely behind are Finland, Switzerland, and the UK, with respective inequality-adjusted education indices of 0.914, 0.907, 0.902, and

0.901. Egypt stands out as a nation with a significantly high level of human development. However, it is noteworthy that within this group, Egypt also exhibits the highest level of inequality, with a rate of 22.1%. Furthermore, when considering the inequality-adjusted education index, Egypt's score is only 0.522. Uzbekistan, a country classified as having a high level of human development, has attained a commendably low level of educational inequality, specifically at 0.6%. This achievement is reflected in its inequality-adjusted education index, which stands at 0.739. Nevertheless, it is worth noting that Egypt exhibited the most pronounced disparity in education, as indicated by a substantial inequality rate of 36.9% and an inequality-adjusted education score of 0.443. Among countries classified as having medium human development, Kyrgyzstan exhibited the most minimal levels of education inequality, as only 3.4% of its population possessed an inequality-adjusted education index of 0.721.

In contrast, Bhutan had the most pronounced disparity in education, with a recorded rate of 48.2%. This disparity is reflected in the country's inequality-adjusted education index, which stands at 0.279. The education disparity in India stands at 36.9%, with a corresponding inequality-adjusted education index of merely 0.348. Tanzania, a country with low human development, accounted for 27.0% of the overall inequality in education. Furthermore, it attained a value of 0.342 for the inequality-adjusted education index. In contrast, Guinea exhibits a notable disparity in educational attainment, with an inequality rate of 50.1%. Furthermore, when considering the inequality-adjusted education index, Guinea's score is a mere 0.172. Therefore, the presence of educational inequality significantly impacts the process of human development, finally resulting in obstacles to achieving sustainable development (Table 2).

Table 2. Inequality in Education

Very high human development	Inequality in education (%)	Inequality adjusted education index (2021)
Czechia	1.3	0.868
New Zealand	1.8	0.914
Slovakia	1.7	0.819
Russia	2.0	0.846
USA	2.7	0.883
UK	2.8	0.901
Canada	2.5	0.893
Finland	2.4	0.907
Australia	3.1	0.896
Switzerland	2.0	0.902
Kuwait	22.1	0.522
High human development		
Uzbekistan	0.6	0.739
Fiji	2.6	0.753
Armenia	2.9	0.720
Ukraine	3.6	0.758
Egypt	36.9	0.443
Medium human development		
Kyrgyzstan	3.4	0.721
Venezuela	8.7	0.663
India	36.9	0.348
Bhutan	48.2	0.279
Nepal	41.1	0.311
Low human development		
Guinea	50.1	0.172
Tanzania	27.0	0.342
Pakistan	43.5	0.221
Niger	35.0	0.172
Gambia	47.0	0.221

Source: HDR-2021-22

he Gender Gap in Higher Education and Research

Historically, women and marginalized genders have faced numerous barriers to entry and advancement in higher education and research. These include biases, stereotypes, a lack of representation in leadership positions, and unequal access to resources and opportunities. As a result, the gender gap persists, with women and non-binary individuals underrepresented in fields such as science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) and often underpaid compared to their male counterparts.

The Need for Gender-Responsive Management

Gender-responsive management is a holistic approach that addresses the systemic inequalities in academia. It encompasses policies, practices, and cultural shifts that promote diversity and inclusion. The importance of gender-responsive management in higher education and research can be highlighted as follows:

1. **Representation:** Encouraging diversity in leadership positions and decision-making bodies ensures that the needs and concerns of all genders are considered.
2. **Equal Opportunities:** Implementing policies that foster equality in recruitment, promotion, and pay scales can help rectify historical biases.
3. **Work-Life Balance:** Providing flexible work arrangements, parental leave, and child care facilities supports the academic progression of individuals, irrespective of their gender.
4. **Mentorship and Sponsorship:** Encouraging mentorship and sponsorship programs can help women and marginalized genders access networks and resources crucial for career development.
5. **Research Focus:** Encouraging gender-responsive research helps to identify and rectify gender-based disparities within higher education and research.
6. **Cultural Shift:** Promoting a culture of respect and inclusion that condemns sexism, harassment, and discrimination is paramount in creating an equitable environment.

Challenges in Implementing Gender-Responsive Management

While the benefits of gender-responsive management are clear, there are challenges to its implementation. These include resistance to change, a lack of awareness, and budget constraints. However, these challenges can be addressed through sustained effort and a commitment to creating more inclusive academic environments.

Opportunities for Progress

The shift towards gender-responsive management in higher education and research also presents numerous opportunities:

1. **Innovation:** Diverse perspectives lead to innovative ideas and solutions, enriching the quality and depth of research.

2. **Global Competitiveness:** Institutions that promote gender equality are more attractive to students and researchers, enhancing their global competitiveness.
3. **Sustainable Development:** Gender-responsive research contributes to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals by addressing gender inequalities in education, health, and economic participation.
4. **Social Justice:** Gender-responsive management aligns with broader movements for social justice, promoting a fair and equitable society.

CONCLUSION

Undoubtedly, the subsequent procedures outlined below possess both theoretical and practical feasibility, as enumerated:

The issue of gender inequality in education necessitates a comprehensive examination from a sociological perspective. 2) There is a need for increased focus on studying panel data analysis in order to gain a clearer understanding of the relationship between education and gender equality. 3) It is important to establish a connection between the process and outcomes of educational decision-making and access to education in a comprehensive analysis of the current educational system. 4) Further investigation is required to explore the relationship between gender and institutional development, particularly in relation to the relevant authorities. 5) It is crucial to conduct more significant research on international comparisons in order to gain a deeper understanding of the subject matter. The objective of achieving gender equality via education as a sustainable development goal is to ensure successful preparation. The primary obstacle in current research on gender inequality in education is to produce analytical literature that examines the specific gender impacts, in order to establish a more theoretically grounded understanding of women's status within the educational system. This theoretical foundation is crucial for effectively addressing the challenges associated with achieving gender equality in economic, historical, cultural, and political contexts in the future (Jacobs, 1996). Primarily, our current academic landscape is characterised by a prevailing male influence, resulting in a lack of success for gender equality initiatives within higher education. This failure can be attributed to various factors,

including the inherent characteristics, structures, and cultural norms of the educational organisation. These elements, whether explicitly or implicitly, serve to advance the careers of male individuals while impeding the progress of their female counterparts. Consequently, this situation can be likened to a metaphorical seven-headed dragon. The aforementioned source posits that there is an attempt to diminish the worth, segregate, marginalise, and ostracise women (O'Connor, 2020). According to the World Economic Forum's study (2023), it is anticipated that the educational gender disparity will be resolved by the year 2038, based on current projections.

REFERENCES

1. British Council. (2021, November). Analysis of factors impacting gender parity in higher education in the state of Andhra Pradesh, India. [Link]
2. Cabolis, C. (2018, February). Gender inequality and R&D. IMD Research and Knowledge. [Link]
3. Canadian International Development Agency. (1999). CIDA's policy on Gender Equality. [Link]
4. Casad, B.J., Franks, J.E., Garasky, C.E., Kittleman, M.M., Roesler, A.C., Hall, D.Y., & Petzel, Z.W. (2020, October). Gender inequality in academia: Problems and solutions for women faculty in STEM. *Journal of Neuroscience Research*, 99(1), 1-11.
5. Cislak, A., Formanowicz, M., & Saguy, T. (2018). Bias against research on gender bias. *Scientometrics*, 115, 189-200.
6. Clark, R. (1992). Multinational corporate investment and women's participation in higher education in noncore nations. *Sociology of Education*, 65, 37-47.
7. Council of Europe. (n.d.). Gender Equality. [Link]
8. Durrani, N., & Halai, A. (2020). Gender Equality, Education and Development: Tension between Global National, and Local Policy Discourses in postcolonial context.

9. European Institute for Gender Equality. (2016). Gender equality in academia and research: GEAR tool. [Link]
10. EU Commission. (n.d.). Gender equality in research and innovation. HORIZON-MONTHLY FOCUS. [Link]
11. Galan-Muros, V. (2023, March). The representation of women in academic and higher education management positions. Policy Brief. UNESCO-IESALO. [Link]
12. García-González, J., Forcén, P., & Jimenez-Sanchez, M. (2019). Men and women differ in their perception of gender bias in research institutions. PLoS ONE, 14(12), e0225763.
13. Hao, J., Zhang, P., & Yu, W. (2021). Gender differences in rural education in China. Asian Journal of Women's Studies, 27(1), 66-86.
14. Huang, J., Gates, A.J., Sinatra, R., & Barabási, A.l. (2020, February). Historical comparison of gender inequality in scientific careers across countries and disciplines. PNAS, 117(9), 4609-4616.
15. iPleaders. (2022, March 22). Government policies for gender equalities in India. [Link]
16. Jacobs, J.A. (1996). Gender Inequality and Higher Education. Annual Review of Sociology, 22, 153-85.
17. Karak, S., & Sen, K. (2017, November). A study on Gender inequality in higher education in Indian context. PANCHAKOTESAYS, 8(2), 111-115. [Link]
18. Klasen, S., & Lamanna, F. (2008, March). The Impact of Gender Inequality in Education and Employment on Economic Growth in Developing Countries: Updates and Extensions. (A background paper for the World Bank Flagship Report). [Link]
19. Liu, F., Holme, P., Chiesa, M., AlShebli, B., & Rahwan, T. (2023). Gender inequality and self-publication are common among academic editors. Nature Human Behaviour, 7, 353-364.

20. Luo, Y., Guo, F., & Li, R. (2021). Gender equality and expansion of higher education: Testing effectively maintained inequality theory against the case of China. *International Journal of Educational Research*, 110.
21. Manjulata., & Sapna, K. (2018). Gender Inequality in Higher Education. *RJPSSs*, 44(2).
[Link]
22. Mott, H. (2022, March). Gender equality in higher education: maximizing impact. [Link]
23. Nmadu, G., Avidime, S., Oguntunde, O., Dashe, V., Abdulkarim, B., & Mandara, M. (2010, September). Girl Child Education: Rising to the Challenge. *African Journal of Reproductive Health*, (Special Issue), 14(3), 107-112.
24. O'Connor, P. (2020). Why is it so difficult to reduce gender inequality in male-dominated higher educational organizations? A feminist institutional perspective. *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews*, 45(2), 207-228.
25. OECD. (n.d.). It's time to close the gender gap in research. [Link]
26. Reeves, R.V., Buckner, E., & Smith, E. (2021, January). The unreported gender gap in high school graduation rates. *UP Front*. [Link]
27. Rosa, R., & Clavero, S. (2022). Gender equality in higher education and research. *Journal of Gender Studies*, 31(1), 1-7.
28. Salik, M., & Zhiyong, Z. (2014, March). Gender Discrimination and Inequalities in Higher Education: A Case Study of Rural Areas of Pakistan. *Academic Research International*, 5(2), 269-276.
29. Sen, A. (1992). *Inequality Re-examined*. Oxford University Press. [Link]
30. Silander, C., Haake, U., & Lindberg, L. (2013). The different worlds of academia: a horizontal analysis of gender equality in Swedish higher education. *Higher Education*, 66(2), 173-188.